

УДК 811.111-26
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19333016

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Специфика формирования и развития образа персонажа в литературно-художественном дискурсе (на примере сказок О. Уайльда)

Аннотация. В статье проведен анализ особенностей формирования и эволюции образа персонажа в литературно-художественном дискурсе на примере сказок Оскара Уайльда. В качестве исследовательского материала были выбраны произведения: «Счастливый принц», «Мальчик-звезда» и «Самолюбивый великан». Актуальность исследования определяется возросшим интересом лингвистики к изучению механизмов языковой репрезентации образа в художественных произведениях. В исследовании используется дискурсивный подход, рассматривающий персонажа как продукт взаимодействия языковых, когнитивных и культурных факторов. Научная новизна работы заключается в определении и оценке языковых и стилистических средств, обеспечивающих динамичность и многослойность образа персонажа. Результаты анализа показывают, что использование оценочной лексики и стилистических приёмов способствует созданию выразительных и запоминающихся образов, отражающих моральные и эстетические ценности эпохи.

Ключевые слова: литературно-художественный дискурс, репрезентация образа, образ персонажа, дискурсивный подход, стилистические средства.

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The Specificity of the Formation and Development of the Character Image in Literary Discourse (Based on O. Wilde's tales)

Abstract. This article analyzes the formation and evolution of character images in literary discourse using Oscar Wilde's fairy tales as an example. The works "The Happy Prince", "The Star-Child", and "The Vanity Giant" were selected as research material. The relevance of this study stems from the growing interest in linguistics in studying the mechanisms of linguistic representation of character in works of fiction. The study utilizes a discursive approach, examining character as a product of the interaction of linguistic, cognitive, and cultural factors. The scientific novelty of this work lies in its identification and evaluation of the linguistic and stylistic devices that ensure the dynamism and multilayered nature of character imagery. The results of the analysis demonstrate that the use of evaluative vocabulary and stylistic devices contributes to the creation of expressive and memorable images that reflect the moral and aesthetic values of the era.

Key words: artistic discourse, character representation, character image, discursive approach, stylistic devices.

In linguistics, artistic discourse is defined as a dynamic form of communication that combines linguistic units with extra-linguistic factors [4]. A literary text in this context is seen as an event integrated within a socio-cultural context, incorporating the subjective evaluations of the author. Unlike other types of discourse, artistic discourse focuses on creating a fictional world and exploring historical and ethical themes, without concern for factual accuracy [3].

Central to artistic discourse is the character image, which represents the author's worldview and the moral-aesthetic paradigms of the era. Thus, the image is impersonated through a "lexical framework", stylistic and pragmatic coloring, as well as through value markers, which makes it possible to determine the cultural and epochal component of the image.

In linguistics, the character image is not a static portrait, but a multi-layered construction created through stylistic devices such as metaphors, epithets, comparisons and antithesis [4; 7]. These devices emphasize the character's external features, emotional impact, and psychological complexity, enhancing the aesthetic experience for the reader [1; 6]. Moreover, allegories with ethical undertones are not limited to superficial details in artistic genre. They create a deep emotional impact by transforming the character from passive to active through the use of figurative language and semantic emphasis [2].

The methodological basis of this research is grounded in discursive analysis. Within the framework of the discursive approach, special attention is paid to the processes of forming images, meanings and value orientations represented through linguistic means. The analysis of the character's image acquires special significance when studying works in which the moral-philosophical content is closely related to the linguistic organization of the text. In this

regard, O. Wilde's tales represent unique material for observations.

This study on the discursive mechanisms for character image formation in O. Wilde's fairy tales is based on the practical material found in "The Happy Prince", "The Star-Child", and "The Selfish Giant". These literary works represent the author's allegorical style, which uses narrative to explore the moral transformation of characters in a fictional world that integrates elements of symbolism and ethical dilemmas.

The tale "The Happy Prince" is a story about a statue of the Prince, which is an allegory exploring themes such as human compassion, self-sacrifice, and the beauty of the soul. The author creates the image of the main character through the convergence of stylistic devices. Thus, the first appearance of the character image is described through epithets: "*fine gold*", "*bright sapphires*", "*large red ruby*" [8, p. 10–13].

These epithets illustrate the Prince as a perfectly beautiful but cold, soulless object, highlighting his excellence. Besides, this image is also created through comparisons:

– "*He is as beautiful as a weathercock*" [8, p. 12];

– "*His hands; are like withered leaves*" [8, p. 13].

With the help of these comparisons, O. Wilde makes the statue only the lifeless symbol of perfection. Moreover, these comparisons ridicule the society that values form over inner content.

Then, at the stage of image transformation, the Prince is depicted as a creature which possesses sensibility and spirituality: "*The poor Prince*" [8, p. 16].

The epithet shows that his beauty now is not just in external appearance, but in internal qualities such as mercy and kindness. The language unit "*poor*" transmits his humility and selflessness.

Furthermore, O. Wilde actively uses evaluative language to express his attitudes towards his characters and society. The

evaluative language is used to show the transformation that happens to the Prince after he loses his jewels. For example, O. Wilde uses it in the comments of passers-by who describe the statue as:

- “<...> *how shabby the Happy Prince looks!*” [8, p. 19];
- “*he is little better than a beggar!*” [8, p. 19].

This language has an ironic tone that shows the author’s assessment of society’s spiritual blindness, as they only notice outward appearances of beauty and not the true beauty of mercy and sacrifice.

Also, there is an allegory at the end of the story: “<...> *the leaden heart and the dead bird*” [8, p. 20].

It expresses that true wealth is not measured in gold, but in love and sacrifice. This depicts the highest level of the Prince’s image development as a literary character, who symbolizes spiritual beauty.

The next tale, “The Selfish Giant”, is about the spiritual awakening of a person who transforms from selfishness towards kindness, repentance, and inner harmony.

At the beginning, the Giant is depicted as cold, proud, and possessive. His characterization is created through evaluative and descriptive language. The epithet “*selfish*” [8, p. 30] immediately defines his moral flaw and central trait. The author also uses direct speech to emphasize his egocentric worldview: “*My own garden is my own garden, anyone can understand that, and I will allow nobody to play in it but myself*” [8, p. 30].

A central allegorical image in the story is the Giant’s garden, which represents his inner world. When he is selfish and unkind, the garden turns into a lifeless, frozen place — a mirror of his cold heart. The elements of nature show the Giant’s soul connection through personification: “*The Snow covered up the grass with her great white cloak, and the Frost painted all the trees silver*” [8, p. 31].

Through this technique, O. Wilde externalizes inner emotions: the eternal winter

symbolizes the frozen soul that has lost the warmth of love.

Furthermore, the stage of transformation begins when the Giant sees children secretly returning to his garden. For example: “*The trees were so glad to have the children back again that they had covered themselves with blossoms*” [8, p. 32].

This example shows that through the personification of the trees in combination with the epithet “*glad*”, the author illustrates the rebirth of life and the awakening of emotion. The environment itself becomes a metaphorical mirror of the Giant’s conscience.

The return of the children and the coming of spring symbolize the revival of his soul. The garden, once frozen, now blooms again — showing the restoration of the Giant’s humanity and the rebirth of his inner life. The epithet “*poor little*” and the lexical unit “*the Giant’s heart melted*” mark the turning point — the awakening of love and compassion.

A key stylistic element which marks the highest point of the Giant’s transformation is the metaphor: “<...> *his heart melted*” [8, p. 33].

Thus, it signals the breakdown of his inner “ice” and the emergence of empathy.

When the mysterious child appears, it employs a biblical allusion and symbolic imagery. This sacred imagery transforms the Giant’s story from a simple moral fable into a parable of redemption. The metaphor “*the wounds of Love*” introduces a new spiritual dimension – love as sacrifice and divine forgiveness.

Finally, the closing description of the Giant “*all covered with white blossoms*” [8, p. 35] after his death serves as a stylistic culmination of purity and peace. The epithet “*white*” and the motif of blossoming carry connotations of innocence and eternal life, finalizing the symbolic parallel between the renewed garden and the redeemed soul.

The following tale, “The Star-Child”, is an allegory that explores themes such as pride, repentance, and the transformation of the human soul through love and humility.

Initially, the Star-Child is described through numerous epithets and comparisons that emphasize his external beauty and celestial origin: “white and delicate as sawn ivory”, “his hair like the daffodil’s ring”, “his eyes like violets by a river of pure water” [8, p. 180].

These stylistic devices idealize the boy, presenting him as beautiful, pure, and otherworldly. However, this excessive perfection serves to foreshadow his moral flaw, which is pride. O. Wilde thus contrasts the boy’s physical beauty with his inner cruelty, which is revealed through evaluative language such as “proud”, “selfish”, and “cruel” [8, p. 181]. The language of moral judgment establishes the author’s critical stance and exposes the gap between appearance and essence.

At the following stage, when the boy denies his mother, evaluative and emotionally charged expressions dominate the narration:

- “Thou art too foul to look at!” [8, p. 183];
- “<...> a beggar and in rags” [8, p. 183].

Through this harsh and degrading language, O. Wilde conveys the Star-Child’s arrogance and moral blindness. The subsequent allegorical transformation of his face into that of “a toad” and his body “scaled like an adder” [6, p. 184] externalizes his inner corruption. These comparisons turn

moral ugliness into visible physical deformity, symbolizing divine punishment for pride.

During the next stage of image transformation, the language and imagery shift from cruelty to humility. Epithets such as “poor”, “weeping”, and “humble” [7, p. 185] highlight the new stage of his moral awakening. The lexical repetition of verbs like “wept”, “bowed”, and “prayed” shows his inner struggle and the beginning of his spiritual rebirth.

Finally, the highest point of the tale plot is the Star-Child’s reunion with his mother: “Mother, I denied thee in the hour of my pride. Accept me in the hour of my humility” [8, p. 185].

This antithesis summarizes the entire path of transformation. The use of the word “mother” emphasizes forgiveness and spiritual reconciliation, while the evaluative lexicon “humility” and “pride” marks the moral poles of the character’s evolution.

To sum up, the use of evaluative language, metaphors, epithets, comparisons, allegories, and other stylistic devices helps reveal the inner development of the character images. These characters undergo a transformation from pride, selfishness, and self-centeredness to spiritual awakening, love, and compassion. Besides, linguistic means also serve to convey the moral and aesthetic values of the time period. Therefore, O. Wilde’s depictions of characters embody the idea that spiritual beauty surpasses external beauty and retains its significance in modern times.

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Поступила в редакцию: 26.03.2026.

Принята в печать: 29.04.2026.